

EFFICACY OF BIO AGENTS AND FUNGICIDES AGAINST *Sclerotium rolfisii* CAUSING COLLAR ROT IN BRINJAL

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Abstract

collar rot caused by *Sclerotium rolfisii* Sacc. is an emerging and destructive disease, especially in nursery and early transplanting stages. The pathogen is known to cause 90–100% yield losses under favourable conditions. The experiment on the management of collar rot diseases of brinjal was conducted during 2023-2024 Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Dhule, Management of collar rot disease were carried out by bioagents and fungicides. The *in vitro* evaluation against *Sclerotium rolfisii*, Tebuconazole 25% EC (T5) showed complete mycelial inhibition (100%), followed by Vitavax 75 WP (T6) with 99.38% inhibition. Among bio agents, *Trichoderma viride* (T1) and *T. harzianum* (T2) were most effective, recording 87.87% and 85.07% inhibition, respectively. Bacterial bioagents, *P. fluorescens* and *B. subtilis*, showed moderate antagonism. Thus, fungicides were superior, but *T. harzianum* and *T. viride* showed strong potential for eco-friendly management of collar rot.

Keyword: Brinjal, *S. rolfisii*, Fungicides, Bioagents, Collar rot.

Introduction

Brinjal, scientifically known as *Solanum melongena*, is a widely cultivated and economically significant vegetable crop belonging to the Solanaceae family. It is commonly referred to as eggplant, a name refers to its egg-shaped fruit. Brinjal is grown primarily in tropical and subtropical regions around the world, with India being one of the largest producers. Known for its versatility in the kitchen, brinjal plays an essential role in many culinary traditions, from curries to stews, and is an integral part of the diet in several cultures. Different cropping system and to study effect of crop response under different cultivation practices.

Collar rot caused by *Sclerotium rolfisii* Sacc is becoming one of the major threats both under nursery and field cultivated brinjal crop. The

Material and methods**In vitro evaluation of fungicides****a) Experimental details:**

Design	:	CRD
Replication	:	Three
Treatment	:	Seven

b) Treatments:**Table 1 List of bioagents and fungicides treatments and their rate of application.**

Tr.No	Treatments	Concentration
1.	<i>Trichoderma viride</i>	1%
2.	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	1%
3.	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	1%
4.	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	1%
5.	Tebuconazole 25% EC	1ml / l
6.	Vitavax 75 WP	2 g/kg
7.	Control	

Observations:**Colony growth (mm):**

Colony diameter (mm) was recorded after inoculation by measuring the radial growth of *Sclerotium rolfisii* using a scale.

Mean Colony Growth = $\frac{\text{Sum of Colony Growth Measurements}}{\text{Number of Replications}}$

2. Percent inhibition:

This determines the effectiveness of bioagents in reducing fungal growth.

$\frac{\text{Growth of pathogen in control plate} - \text{Growth of pathogen in presence of treatment plate}}{\text{Growth of pathogen in control plate}} \times 100$

Per cent inhibition of pathogen = $\frac{\text{Growth of pathogen in control plate} - \text{Growth of pathogen in presence of treatment plate}}{\text{Growth of pathogen in control plate}} \times 100$

Results and Discussion:**In vitro evaluation of bioagents and fungicides against collar rot disease of brinjal caused by *Sclerotium rolfisii***

The effect of bioagents and fungicides on mycelial growth and inhibition of *sclerotium rolfisii* under *in vitro* conditions. The results obtained in respect of colony growth and percent inhibition were presented in table 2.

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Efficacy of four bioagents (*Trichoderma viride*, *Trichoderma harzianum*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Bacillus subtilis*) and two fungicides (Tebuconazole 25% EC, Vitavax 75 WP) were tested against *Sclerotium rolfisii* under *in vitro* condition by poison food technique and dual culture technique.

Effect of bioagents and fungicides on mycelial growth of *Sclerotium rolfisii* under *in vitro* conditions

The *in vitro* evaluation of bioagents and fungicides revealed significant differences in their ability to inhibit mycelial growth of *Sclerotium rolfsii*. Among all treatments, Tebuconazole 25 % EC recorded complete inhibition of the pathogen with 0.00 mm colony diameter. It was at par with Vitavax 75 WP, which also showed strong fungistatic effect with a minimal colony growth of 0.55 mm.

Among bioagents, *Trichoderma viride* was found most effective, showing the lowest colony diameter of 10.92 mm, was at par with *Trichoderma harzianum* (13.61 mm). The bacterial bioagents were comparatively less effective: *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Bacillus subtilis* recorded 17.85 mm and 20.75 mm, respectively. All treatments significantly reduced the growth of *S. rolfsii* compared to the control (90 mm), confirming their antagonistic potential under laboratory conditions.

Banyal et al. (2008) reported that Tebuconazole completely inhibited the mycelial growth of *S. rolfsii*, proving superior to other fungicides. Among bioagents, Suryawanshi et al. (2015) observed maximum inhibition with *Trichoderma viride* (10.93 mm), followed by *T. harzianum* and *P. fluorescens*, while *B. subtilis* showed comparatively lower efficacy. Similar moderate suppression by *P. fluorescens* was also noted by Anilkumar (2008) and Jadon (2009).

Effect of bioagents and fungicides on percent inhibition of *Sclerotium rolfsii* under *in vitro* conditions

The results pertaining to the percent inhibition of *Sclerotium rolfsii* by different bioagents and fungicides under *in vitro* conditions are presented in Table 2. A significant variation was observed among the treatments in their ability to inhibit the mycelial growth of *Sclerotium*

rolfsii under *in vitro* conditions. The fungicides and bioagents tested exhibited different levels of antagonism, as reflected in their percent inhibition values.

Among all treatments, Tebuconazole 25% EC recorded the highest percent inhibition (100%), completely suppressing the mycelial growth of the pathogen, it was at par with Vitavax 75 WP, which showed 99.38% inhibition. These results confirm the superior efficacy of chemical fungicides in restricting the development of *S. rolfsii* under laboratory conditions.

Among the bioagents, *Trichoderma viride* exhibited the maximum inhibition (87.86%), followed by *Trichoderma harzianum* (85.07%), *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (80.17%), and *Bacillus subtilis* (76.86%). These antagonists were able to significantly inhibit the mycelial growth of the pathogen compared to the untreated control, which showed zero inhibition.

The observed trend clearly indicates the superiority of fungicides over biological agents. However, the performance of *T. viride* and *T. harzianum* was also promising, suggesting their potential for eco-friendly management of collar rot in brinjal.

Sujana et al. (2025) reported strong antagonistic effects of *Trichoderma viride* (87.86%) and *T. harzianum* (85.07%) against *Sclerotium rolfsii*, consistent with dual-culture assays in brinjal. In contrast, Kushwaha et al. (2018) observed lower inhibition, with *T. harzianum* (63.60%) performing better than *T. viride* (50.85%). These variations may be due to differences in strains or modes of action like mycoparasitism and metabolite production.

Table 2 : *In vitro* evaluation of bioagents and fungicides against collar rot disease of brinjal caused by *Sclerotium rolfsii*

Tr. No	Treatments	Mean Col. Dia. (mm)*	Inhibition (%)*
T1	<i>Trichoderma viride</i>	10.92	87.87 (69.62)
T2	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	13.61	85.07 (67.27)
T3	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	17.85	80.17 (63.56)
T4	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	20.48	76.86 (61.25)
T5	Tebuconazole 25% EC	0.0	100 (90)
T6	Vitavax 75 WP	0.56	99.38 (85.48)
T7	Control	90.00	0 (0)
	SE	0.55	0.59
	CD @5%	1.6	1.7

*Means of three replications

Figures in parentheses are angular transformed values Dia. = Diameter,

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